

WAYS OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN HIGHER SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

The article analyzes present issues of improving the quality in higher education schools, taking into account the world experience. First and foremost, attention is paid to the concept of the quality of education, interpretations of various scientists and specialists. It is clear that the quality of education depends on the competence and experience of the teacher and the modern technologies. Moreover, parents' inattention to their children is also one of the key causes to obtain and improve education. The article makes a conclusion about the effectiveness of group training methods based on international experience. The article proposes to select students according to their abilities and inclinations to scientific-research activities or work in business structures. The educational process in universities should be aimed at the integration of science, education, industry (business) around the world. The article provides some examples as well.

Key words: education, present issues, quality, world experience, training methods, educators, parents' attention, motivation, modern requirements, knowledge, scientific research activities.

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For the time being, education is the top priority of nations over the world. Initiatives to facilitate students attend higher education schools and improve the quality of education can shift the scenario of growth and prosperity of education. On top of that, the quality and accessibility of education is a key factor in the country's competitiveness. According to the given examples, scientists have come to the conclusion that in the current conditions of the information revolution, the competitive advantages are determined neither by the size of the country, nor by its rich natural resources, or by significant amounts of financial capital. The most essential thing is the level of education and the amount of knowledge accumulated by society. Besides that, knowledge is rapidly becoming obsolete, new knowledge is replacing it, and this process will be repeated endlessly and continuously. Therefore, people need to learn throughout their lives in order to meet modern requirements and needs.

So as to record steady growth and improve the quality of education, certain measures should be taken into consideration. To commence with any solution and transformation it's important to identify the root cause of the issue.

Education has degraded because of multiple reasons including:
Deficiency of parents' attention and motivation to their children
Lack of proper infrastructure
Poor pedagogy skills
Lack of trained teachers

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Using theoretical approaches in imparting knowledge
 Poor assessment/evaluation of the student's learning
 High competition among the institutes or universities

As we see, in today's society parents are the most important personnel to encourage their offsprings to take an education and continue their studies in further education. However, it is pity that most of the parents are very engaged with their duties and responsibilities at their work and they do not have enough time for their children. In the aftermath of this, children are not controlled by their parents and they are involved in unnecessary activities and they are not encouraged to obtain education. As a result of this, teachers have to substitute the responsibility of parents. And this, in turn, directly goes to shoulder of educators. Educators are required to attract students' interests and encourage to further their education. If teachers desire to increase their student enrollment, improving the education quality it delivers is an excellent way to start. Having an improved education quality will not just bring more students to their educational organization, it'll also make their university a reputable educational establishment in this area or across the world.

So there are some ways to overcome these challenges and improve the quality of education and higher schools can evaluate the following factors:

1. Well-maintained infrastructure

Students should be motivated to come to educational establishment by providing the basic amenities required as per norms. Any educational establishment should have a spacious classroom with furniture, board, electrical fittings, clean and hygienic toilets, an activity and play area, laboratories, and a computer lab. But having all those amenities without their proper utilization and maintenance may demotivate a child from going to school. As we know, well-maintained infrastructure creates an environment to learn. Besides that, you need to revise your school's educational programs based on industry changes. As a school owner or educator, it's your obligation to bridge the skills gap that has been an issue in our society. The skills gap refers to the mismatch of graduates' competency and the employers' requirements. Being able to equip students with the right knowledge and skillset is a significant criterion in delivering high-quality education.

2. Proper pedagogy skills

The concept of learning, unlearning and relearning should be implemented over here. Educational establishments need a transition from rote learning to conceptual methods that can keep the teachers and students engaged. The liking or disliking of a subject by students depends on the method of teaching. Teachers and educators need to a wide range of proper pedagogical skills, and they need to know how to enhance and upgrade their teaching skills for a better outcome.

3. Quality of teachers

Most higher schools compromise on quality by hiring teachers at less pay. Teachers are the key elements in the classroom that ignite the minds of students for seeking knowledge and play a crucial role to motivate and encourage students to obtain necessary knowledge. In order to improve teacher quality, they need to be provided with modern teaching aids, tools, and methodologies such as smart classrooms and digital course content. Because taking proper and summative assessments will provide a better understanding of the student. Individual differences should be kept in mind while preparing the evaluation tools which should also include critical/higher order thinking skills.

4. Free-time activities

As it is known pressurizing students will deviate their minds from studies and which may hamper their interest in continuing their education further. For this reason, educational establishment should be involved in various co-curricular activities that serve as a key

component in sustaining students' interest in school. Students should have opportunities to spend their time productively. It should have proper sports facilities and avenues for cultural events that help in building the life skills and personality of the students. Moreover, inter-school competitions should be organized in order to encourage them.

5. Government funding

Government can also have an essential role to improve the quality of education in higher education. They need to motivate students by allocating some amount of money to win. They need to provide the most intelligent students with state scholarships.

6. Assessment and evaluation tools

Teachers and educators should know that taking proper and summative assessments will provide a better understanding of the student. It is significant that individual differences be kept in mind while preparing the evaluation tools which should also include critical/higher order thinking skills. Based on the results, they would be able to evaluate the learning level of the student and by taking the necessary steps, the quality of education can be improved.

7. Community building

It is clear that peer learning is vital at every level. In order to improve the quality of education we can build a school community where all the stakeholders along with the community can come together to share their ideas, challenges, and solutions with others as cross-functional learning. Thus, it will enhance the connectivity and productivity of the educational organizations.

In conclusion, ensuring high quality education is a key issue, as the development of technology and economic growth require highly qualified personnel. Thereby, the problem of ensuring the high quality of education is being paid increasing attention not only to participants in the educational process, but also to scientists and researchers involved in the development of education. As it is mentioned above, the quality of educational services directly affects not only the demand for graduates in the labor market, but also the effectiveness of the educational organization.

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